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SUSTAINABLE LIVING IN UTRECHT: UNDERSTANDING CURRENT PRACTICES AND FUTURE ASPIRATIONS

Results from Autumn 2023 research

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SUMMARY:

This study investigates sustainable living among budget-conscious residents of Utrecht, focusing on their current practices, aspirations, and encountered challenges. Conducted from September to December 2023, it targeted a diverse demographic and employed a mixed-methods approach for data collection, including discussion groups, brainstorming sessions, street interviews, and online surveys. Key findings indicate residents' strong engagement in sustainable behaviours such as choosing plant-based diets, saving resources, managing waste effectively, preferring second-hand goods, and using eco-friendly transportation. Residents expressed aspirations to further adopt sustainable diets, grow their own vegetables, reduce waste and plastic use, minimize air travel, and curb consumerism habits. Obstacles like cost, lack of space, and information gaps were identified. The study concludes with a suite of proposed initiatives aimed at overcoming these barriers. This research underscores the community's commitment to sustainability despite financial constraints and outlines actionable initiatives to address challenges, aiming to guide Utrecht towards a more sustainable and inclusive future.

INTRODUCTION:

In the pursuit of fostering a more sustainable future for Utrecht, the research conducted between September and December 2023 delved into the realm of sustainable living practices among residents operating on a modest budget. The exploration was meticulously organized around three key areas:

1. **Current practices:** This aspect involved the examination of existing sustainable lifestyles and choices adopted by residents in their present day-to-day life. The aim was to uncover the efforts already in place and identify patterns that could serve as models for broader adoption.
2. **Aspirations:** This facet focused on the identification of desires and goals harboured by individual residents for embracing more sustainable living practices in the future.
3. **Challenges:** This focus area aimed at identifying the challenges faced by residents in adopting the mentioned sustainable lifestyles and practices. The aim was to collect valuable insights into the barriers that must be addressed to make sustainable living more accessible and feasible for all.

The overarching goal of this investigation is to generate valuable insights that can inform the development of policies, initiatives, and community-driven efforts, fostering a more inclusive and sustainable Utrecht.

TARGET GROUP:

The study encompassed a diverse demographic, ensuring that the findings are representative of the varied perspectives within the low-budget strata of Utrecht residents. The characteristics of the surveyed group are as follows:

- *Age range:* The age range of the participants spanned a broad spectrum, with a notable emphasis on young individuals.
- *Cultural backgrounds:* Our research prioritized a rich and diverse representation of cultural backgrounds, recognizing the intersectionality of sustainable living.
- *Residency:* Surveyed participants were residents of different neighbourhoods and locations within Utrecht, reflecting varied living condition and contexts in the city.
- *Occupation:* The surveyed group exhibited a diverse range of occupations, bringing together individuals from varied professional backgrounds. Notably, there was a significant presence of students.
- *Socioeconomic status:* A central theme that unifies the surveyed group was the overarching emphasis on budget-conscious living.

METHODOLOGY:

In order to capture the multifaceted nature of sustainability, our methodology embraced a mixed-methods approach, allowing us to gather insights from a broad spectrum of settings.

1. Discussion and Focus Groups:

These interactive sessions provided the perfect platform for in-depth conversations and collective exploration of sustainable living practices. The following groups were organized:

- a. Discussion group with visitors of the Voorkamer.
- b. Discussion group with members of the AZC.
- c. Focus group in collaboration with the “First-Generation Low Income Scholarship Students” at the University College Utrecht.

2. Silent Anonymous Brainstorming:

This methodology was employed to encourage creative and candid contributions, allowing participants to share thoughts without inhibition:

- a. Clothes Swap in Collaboration with Buurtbel Wittevrouten.
- b. Sustainability Week at University College Utrecht

3. Street Interviews:

Street interviews serve as a dynamic approach to capture spontaneous responses and opinions from participants in various locations within Utrecht.

- a. Science Park: academic community.
- b. City Centre: broader demographic.

4. Online Survey:

This approach was designed to ensure a wide reach and allows for both quantitative analysis and qualitative exploration.

RESULTS:

Current Sustainable Practices

The investigation into current sustainable practices among Utrecht residents with limited budgets revealed a wide array of environmentally conscious behaviours. This showcased a commitment to sustainable living practices within the constraints of budgetary considerations.

- *Diet and Food Choices:* A predominant theme among participants was the conscious choice of plant-based, vegetarian, and organic food options. This reflects a growing awareness of the environmental impact of dietary choices.
- *Water and Energy Conservation:* Participants demonstrated a commitment to water and energy conservation through mindful habits, including water reuse and energy-efficient practices. This finding highlights a collective effort to minimize the ecological footprint associated with daily routines.
- *Waste Management:* The investigation revealed an informed approach to waste management, with participants actively sorting and minimizing their waste.
- *Shopping and Consumption:* In the realm of consumption, a prevalent trend emerged wherein participants prioritized second-hand purchases and embraced reusable products. Additionally, a notable engagement in upcycling practices was observed, showcasing a commitment to sustainable choices even in the era of consumerism.
- *Transportation:* Participants exhibited sustainable transportation choices, with a significant preference towards public transportation and biking. This not only aligns with eco-friendly practices but also reflects a practical approach to cost-effective commuting.
- *Social Engagement:* An interesting aspect of the results was the active participation of individuals in social engagement events and education initiatives related to sustainability. This underscores the importance of community-driven initiatives and educational programs in fostering a culture of sustainable living.

Aspirations for Sustainable Living and Related Challenges

1. Adopting a Sustainable Diet

Participants expressed a strong aspiration to adopt a sustainable diet characterized by choices such as plant-based, vegetarian, and organic food options. This reflects a conscious effort to align dietary habits with environmental sustainability principles.

Challenges:

- Parental resistance to dietary change.
- Cost of meat substitutes and organic products.

Possible Initiatives:

- Informative Resources on Plant-Based and Organic Food Benefits.

- **Vegan Cooking Workshops:** This initiative could equip individuals with practical skills and knowledge to integrate sustainable choices into their daily meals.
- **Vegan/Organic Food Vouchers:** Introducing vegan or organic food vouchers would address the financial constraints associated with the adoption of a sustainable diet, making eco-friendly food options more accessible to a broader demographic.

2. *Grow Own Vegetables*

Participants expressed the aspiration to cultivate their own vegetables, symbolizing a commitment to self-sufficiency and a desire to engage in local, organic sourcing practices.

Challenges:

- Limited space, particularly in urban environments.
- Modern lifestyle constraint.

Possible Initiatives:

- **Tile-Flipping:** With tile-flipping initiatives, individuals could repurpose the underutilized spaces in the streets and create small vegetable patches. This initiative provides a tangible, hands-on approach to overcome spatial challenges.
- **Community Garden Network:** Establishing a community garden network would foster collaboration and shared spaces for vegetable cultivation.
- **Home-Friendly Gardening Workshop:** Conducting home-friendly gardening workshops focused on container gardening, vertical gardening, and other space-efficient techniques, is an educational initiative that would equip individuals with practical skills for cultivating vegetables within the limitations of their homes and would empower them to integrate gardening seamlessly into their modern lifestyles.

3. *Separating Waste*

Participants expressed the aspiration of responsibly separating waste.

Challenges:

- Logistical difficulties in student housing.
- Lack of information on correct separation practices.

Possible Initiatives:

- **Educational Workshops:** Conducting educational workshops covering the basics of waste separation, recycling practices, and the environmental impact of responsible waste management would be a proactive initiative to address the lack of information.
- **Customized Bin System + Composting Bins:** Introducing a customized bin system that includes clearly labelled bins for different types of waste could

be an effective initiative. Additionally, incorporating composting bins can encourage participants to embrace composting as part of their waste separation routine.

- Collaboration with Student Housing: Implementing centralized waste separation systems within student housing complexes addresses space constraints and promotes a collective commitment to waste management.

4. *Aspiration: Reduce Plastic Consumption*

Individuals expressed a shared aspiration to reduce plastic consumption, showcasing a commitment to mitigating environmental impact through mindful consumer choices.

Challenges:

- Excessive plastic packaging in everyday products.
- Accessibility and (initial) affordability of plastic-free products.

Possible Initiatives:

- Containers Giveaway: Providing reusable containers for plastic-free products addresses the economic barriers associated with the initial affordability of sustainable alternatives.
- Community Zero-Waste Guides: Creating a guide encompassing information on local stores offering plastic-free products, DIY alternatives, and tips for minimizing plastic use in daily life would offer practical advice on reducing plastic consumption.

5. *Aspiration: Reduce Air Travel*

Individuals expressed a sincere aspiration to reduce air travel, aligning with the commitment of mitigating the environmental impact associated with long-distance flights.

Challenges:

- Economic prohibitions of other transportation means.
- Lack of efficiency for long-distance travel.

Possible Initiatives:

- Affordable Transportation Packages: Implementing affordable transportation packages offering cost-effective solutions for alternative means such as trains or buses could make sustainable transportation more financially accessible and competitive with air travel.
- Investment in Sustainable Transportation Infrastructure: Addressing the efficiency concern requires strategic investment in sustainable transportation infrastructure.

6. *Aspiration: Reduce Consumerism Habits*

Individuals expressed a shared aspiration to reduce consumerism habits, signifying a commitment to mindful and sustainable consumption practices.

Challenges:

- Time commitment associated with adopting reduced consumerism habits.
- Lack of awareness about sustainable consumption choices.

Possible Initiatives:

- Minimalist Living/Repair Workshop: These workshops can provide practical insights, strategies, and resources for individuals looking to improve their consumeristic lifestyles, encouraging a shift toward mindful consumption.
- Community Guides: Establishing community guides would address both time commitment and lack of awareness challenges.

CONCLUSION:

This comprehensive research of Utrecht residents' current practices and future aspirations for sustainable living has uncovered a rich tapestry of environmentally conscious behaviours and ambitious aspirations. The findings underscore a considerable commitment to sustainable practices despite the constraints of budgetary considerations, reflecting a community that recognizes and values the relevance of individual actions in the broader environmental well-being. The identified challenges pave the way for tailored initiatives aimed at bridging the gap between individuals' aspirations and realizations. As we look towards 2024, follow-up activities could include further engagement with community members to refine and adapt strategies, the implementation of pilot projects based on the proposed initiatives, and the establishment of partnerships with local businesses and institutions to support sustainability goals. The findings provide a robust foundation for policymakers, community leaders, and stakeholders to design and implement targeted interventions that will push Utrecht towards a more sustainable future accessible to all.

ANNEX: REPORTS FROM DIALOGUES AND SURVEYS

STREET SURVEYS AT SCIENCE PARK - LET THE STUDENTS SPEAK!

GIULIA AND OLLIE INTERVIEW STUDENTS ABOUT ACCESSIBLE SUSTAINABILITY: WHAT DO THEY HAVE TO SAY?

By Ollie Köhn-Haskins

So, what did we learn?

When asked about individual, everyday actions, students prioritized **three main topics**: recycling, eating less animal products, and most importantly, sustainable transportation. Interestingly, many students almost **immediately included suggestions on what the government or education system could improve** in their answers about individual actions. Although **most agreed that individual actions make a difference** (unfortunately not all of them!), they emphasized that **there needs to be policy change** to create a sustainable and socially just Utrecht. Implementing changes at Universities is a wonderful place to start, as they reach many people, and tend to impact new social norms or trends.

- *Recycling*

Students were proud to report that they were careful to separate different kinds of waste.

However, there could be some areas of improvement: one student admitted to not knowing what to do with special kinds of waste such as lightbulbs or batteries. Although she knows there are places available to throw these out, they are inconveniently located and not made transparent - especially to English speakers in Utrecht.

Additionally, students rightfully complained about the lack of public water fountains in Utrecht. They said that it is useless for them to buy a reusable water bottle if there is nowhere to fill it up (or only in private restrooms, for examples). They also raised concerns about people who are too poor to afford buying water: Water is a basic human right and should be available to all!

- *Eating less animal products*

Although we did not interview any vegetarians or vegans, many students stated that they were trying to avoid animal products as much as possible. I am fully vegan myself, but I think any step towards eating less animal products are a step in the right direction! Putting too much pressure on yourself to be 100% vegan to begin with can be extremely discouraging, so I congratulate anyone who is trying to make a change, no matter how small.

One student brought up the fact that vegan meat replacements are much too expensive for most students to afford. I agree with her: all I can afford to buy regularly is tofu, so I have to get creative with cooking! Perhaps the municipality could work on subsidizing vegan products and taxing meat more heavily.

- *Sustainable transportation*

The main focus in all our conversations revolved around the question of transportation. Most students said that they biked almost everywhere. However, international students, who go back home during the holidays, reflected on the environmental cost of flying. Unfortunately, though, due to government subsidies, flying has become a much cheaper option than catching an international train. This needs to change now. Flying is one of the main contributors to CO2 emissions, and decreasing flights, or making them more expensive and using this profit to invest in sustainability, could make a big difference for our future.

Some students have to commute across the Netherlands to get to university. One student, who lives in The Hague (due to the housing crisis) but studies in Utrecht, shared that she has to spend 30 euros *three times a week* just to be able to attend classes. This eats away the majority of her weekly income. Why are the trains privatized? Why does everything have to come back to profit? If Utrecht wants to be socially just, it must be socially just for all. Education should not have to be this costly.

Hopefully this short reflection is some food for thought, and I look forward to working with Giulia in the future to find out more about **sustainable living for all in Utrecht!**

SUSTAINABLE LIVING AT THE CLOTHES SWAP

YOUNG PEOPLE SHARED THEIR IDEAS FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVING WITH A SMALL PURSE

By Giulia Malisani

On Saturday 4 November 2023, we attended the Clothing Swap event organized by [Buurtbel Wittevrouwen](#), where we also led a small silent brainstorming session. During this activity, participants had the opportunity to reflect on their aspirations for a more sustainable lifestyle. We gathered many fresh and disparate ideas and insights, ranging from eco-friendly practices to more conscious choices. In parallel, we delved into the individual challenges they face on their journey toward sustainability. Overall, the brainstorming turned out to be an inspirational twist, allowing everyone to contribute their vision for a greener world. We are committed to presenting the findings from this and other collaborative events to the Utrecht municipality with the aim of designing new projects geared toward making sustainable living more accessible and achievable for all. Join us at our upcoming brainstorming events to add your voice to this sustainable future! Check out the agenda [here](#).

SUSTAINABLE LIVING FOR STUDENTS

FOCUS GROUP DURING GREEN WEEK AT UNIVERSITY COLLEGE UTRECHT CAMPUS

By Ineke Malsch

Four women and three men brainstormed about stimulating students living at the campus of the [University College Utrecht](#) (UCU) to live more sustainably, with specific attention to the needs and wishes of low-income students. The focus group was organised by the UCU Green Team and Federation of Low-Income Scholarship Students (FLISS), during lunch time on 16 November 2023.

The meeting started with introductions of [Duurzaam Utrecht 2030](#), where Elizabete and Giulia are active as [interns](#), and of FLISS. In Duurzaam Utrecht 2030, Elizabete is working on a report on the trial with [subsidised organic groceries](#) in Lunetten, and we have proposed a follow up project addressing the [challenge](#) to regularly supply the food banks with fresh and healthy produce. Recommendations for facilitating [organic food for all](#) in Utrecht will be presented in the Domkerk on 15 December, 16.00-18.00 hrs. Giulia is organising dialogue events and street interviews to collect more wishes for sustainable living with a low income from more diverse stakeholder communities. This will inform the priorities for Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 in the coming years.

FLISS is an independent student body, initiated by UCU students. It is a support network on campus allowing first-generation low-income scholarship students to talk about difficulties they encounter. It is open to anyone who feels they have a low income, has to work two or three side jobs, or take a heavy student loan. They organise workshops on financial aspects, and are preparing a presentation for the tutor network, to raise awareness of their existence, so tutors can inform students about it. The tutor system is the only organisation on campus reaching out to every student.

How to make life on campus more sustainable for students with low-income backgrounds? What difficulties on campus are due to low incomes?

Food choices are problematic. As a vegetarian, the advantage is that meat is more expensive, but still, you are not able to buy organic, because it is too expensive. Proteins for vegetarians are very expensive, like nuts or vega-burgers. A completely vegetable, carbon-based menu is not healthy.

In addition, some organic food is packaged, for example at AH or Jumbo. The shop Sweet Greens does not sell organic produce, but it is a zero-waste shop, selling oil, fresh humus, and feta without packaging.

What would make you buy more organic or fresh produce?

If it is cheaper. Or if it is sold at the nearest supermarket, PLUS. However, for many products, PLUS is not the cheapest. You can also get a subscription to "groentetas", but then you have to fetch it off campus at a specific time. Sweet greens are next to the Jumbo. It is unclear if it is cheaper or more expensive. A suggestion is to create a website for comparing prices of organic and not-organic food. [Milieucentrum Utrecht](#) (MCU) already hosts an [online database](#) of sustainable shops in Utrecht, but the listed retailers are mostly in the city centre. A suggestion for them could be to also include initiatives like clothes swaps or the giveaway shop of [Stichting Limoenz](#) in Lunetten. Besides asking MCU to expand their database, the UCU Green Team could also develop their own database, by collecting entries through google forms and putting them on a map. This can be used to raise awareness of first year students where to find organic food, vintage clothes, zero-waste stores, and cheaper options. On one's own it can take two years to discover all the places. In Latvia, zero-waste stores are easily accessible. In the Netherlands, zero-waste

shopping is only just starting. [Loos Utrecht](#) recently opened a zero-waste grocery store near the campus. Before the summer, they came with a bike on campus, on Friday mornings, which was an awkward timing for students. Tuesday afternoon would be better. On the other hand, the shop is only ten minutes walking. How to get students to venture off-campus? Awareness is the biggest issue. The campus is located in a wealthy neighbourhood. Cheaper shops are further away. Are students motivated to go further than 500 metres? We could go with a group, to increase the motivation of people to go. For example: Tuesday afternoon sustainable groceries group, or Zero-waste groceries afternoon. Zero-waste stores don't always have containers to put the groceries in. The Green Team is already planning a food exchange shelf in the Newton building, where food is placed in transparent plastic boxes to avoid attracting mice. This can be accompanied by a clean jar collection point. Make sure to tell people to clean the jars before leaving them there. Examples are pesto, jam, or pickle jars.

Should consumerism on campus be addressed? Some students find it unacceptable if people buy clothes from some unsustainable companies and want to call them out. One option is to put up posters for shaming fellow-students, saying "Did you really need that?" It will be important to add data to demonstrate that company X has been doing Y. Information can also be shared on where you can buy other affordable clothes, with a price limit of 5 euro. Getting clothes from a pick-up point is also better than home delivery. The art school has a sewing machine students can use to mend their clothes, but nobody knows about it. Raise awareness: if your clothes are broken, repair them there yourself. A fashion show is coming up, this can be a good opportunity to raise awareness to avoid throwing clothes away. They use mainly second-hand fabrics, almost nothing is bought new. Such fashion shows are organised three times per semester. The upcoming theme is Winter Wonderland. You can also find nice decorations, books, and furniture at recurrent flea markets. Start offering the opportunity for people to leave their things as donations for second hand shops. The Green Team can sort the donations and bring them to the store of the Kringloopwinkel (?).

Students living in the same unit use the Splitser for buying household products for common use. However, not everyone contributes their share, and not everyone benefits equally. There is a shame culture surrounding it. FLISS wants to table discussion about it.

SUSTAINABLE LIVING AND SOCIAL VEGETABLE GARDENING IN LOMBOK

REPORT OF BRAINSTORM IN DE VOORKAMER ON 15 NOVEMBER 2023

By Ineke Malsch

On November 15, Giulia Malisani, Alice Bezett, and I talked to nine other visitors of De Voorkamer about sustainable living and social vegetable gardening, in Dutch, English and Arabic. After a round of introductions, we discussed what the participants themselves are already doing to live sustainably. Someone argued that people with little money already live more sustainably. When he was a kid, there used to be three siblings, and when the clothes became too small for the eldest, the second and finally the youngest got them. His mother sewed her own clothes. With a lot of money, you can buy something new sooner.

In the Netherlands, some things are easier than in the countries where people came from. For example, you can take the bike more easily here than in Italy, and waste separation is a lot easier than in New Zealand. Here you can cycle to the waste separation station, where you can hand in more different things separately, such as wood, paper, metal, or vegetables, fruit, and garden waste. This reduces the amount of incineration or landfill. In Iraq, waste separation has been common since 1980, including for glass, metal, wood, and other materials.

An engineer develops buildings for organizations in his home country. He is studying sustainable design in Utrecht. Years ago, he worked on automated vertical gardens. Growing vegetables was very expensive in his city. This allowed you to save space. Many apartments had roof gardens, where trees and plants can also grow. The terraces in front of the buildings were also planted. In large cities, air pollution from traffic

is a major problem. He created a small garden for the house. The resident should open the window for fresh air and can use the shower water to water the plants.

Another has 30 years of experience growing all kinds of fruit and vegetable trees as a farmer.

Someone else's grandfather used to have an allotment garden in the Netherlands. Back then it was free, now you have to wait a long time before it's your turn.

When asked, participants mentioned examples of sustainability in everyday life: travelling by train, making your home more energy efficient. You can do a lot and it costs a lot of money and time, but you don't see how it affects the world and the climate. Many students feel the same way. Do an individual's actions make sense or not?

Governments and large companies need to do more, but you can do something yourself. It's not an excuse to also start polluting when others are doing it.

Poor people don't have time to worry about sustainability. First, help them get a better life so they can feed their children and live in a good home. Make poor people richer, and then work together on sustainability.

Giulia: Sustainable Utrecht 2030 can help to bridge the gap. We don't have a lot of money, but we can help.

What would you like to do differently to live more sustainably, and what are the challenges? It can be small or big things.

Everything that used to be sustainable and natural is now gone because of technology. No one has time to work in nature. Everyone sits behind the laptop or on the I-phone all day. People live in small spaces. On a farm, you have to have a lot of trees and plants in a small area. In the city, you might be able to put together some kind of farm, if everyone is growing something, and a person is going everywhere to take care of the plants, just like a honeybee.

Someone lives on the 12th floor in a flat, and the whole balcony is full of plants. What else can he do as a farmer?

Maybe we can remove tiles in the neighbourhood and plant something there? According to the municipality, you are not allowed to grow fruit and vegetables in a vegetable garden in Lombok because the soil is contaminated.

Someone is already a sustainable farmer. How does he get his neighbours to help with the gardening? He wants to know more about nature and the planet, and about what the government can and cannot do. Where are gardens already? The Netherlands is an agricultural country, but there are no gardens, at least not in the city. He works as a volunteer in three vegetable gardens and teaches others how to garden.

Giulia: Are there more small things you would like to do to live sustainably? Taking care of nature and plants, using less plastic, using public transport more often, cycling, eating organic food. Another uses clean energy. Someone is using a lot of plastic packaging. At the AH everything is still wrapped in plastic. He has children and a job, so he doesn't have much time. For example, you can use less water, but someone else disagreed. Do not throw plastic and cans on the ground, and separate waste. In the supermarket they sell herbs in plastic, it would be nice if you could grow them yourself.

Someone proposes a project to make crates for growing plants during a workshop with visitors to the Voorkamer that you can place anywhere. It is a modular system of small wooden crates, lined with garbage bags, in which you put a separate self-sewn bag of soil, which you can pick up with sticks. This allows you to put together a small garden on the balcony or in the house. You can also easily swap plants with the neighbours. This person proposed that an artist from De Voorkamer can paint each crate so that they are all unique, that the crates can be sold for a cost of 10 euros or less to the residents of the flats on the Kanaalstraat or in the neighbourhood. Also, that the owner of the sewing shop down the street might be able to figure out a way to stitch it together faster so that it becomes less labour-intensive.

Herbs or trees don't fit, but flowers do. How do you keep the plants alive on the balcony, where they are exposed to sun and wind? Plastic containers are suitable for this.

A concrete request is to ask the municipality for a piece of public green space to start a neighbourhood vegetable garden in or around Lombok with interested volunteers from the Voorkamer and the neighbourhood. There is a suitable location along the Kanaalweg. Previously, there was an art project in

which vegetables were grown in a pick-your-own garden in containers on Westplein: [Lucrative dumpster dives Perron West](#). **Ineke contacts the municipality of Utrecht.**

This is not the same as the project in which people with and without a garden are linked, in which one or more gardeners maintain a vegetable garden in someone's home. This is what Alice Bezett is working on in collaboration with Sustainable Utrecht 2030: <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/en-gb/sociaalmoestuiniieren>.

ENABLE SUSTAINABLE LIVING ON A TIGHT BUDGET

REPORT WORKSHOP 27-11-2023, SOCIAL IMPACT FACTORY AAN DE GRACHT

By Ineke Malsch, Elizabete Fedcenko, Alice Bezett, Giulia Malisani

Twenty people (11 f/9 m) brainstormed about three challenges to make sustainable living possible on a tight budget: organic food, social vegetable gardening and mobility poverty. Giulia Malisani opened the workshop with a short presentation about the mission and vision of [Sustainable Utrecht 2030](#). She led an icebreaker, where participants introduced themselves and shared an Aha moment.

During an open stage, participants talked about what they or their organization contributed to sustainability and social justice in Utrecht. The Food Council in formation wants to combat the current fragmentation in municipal food policy by developing a holistic, green, and social vision. They want to combat both the climate crisis and social inequality. Soon they will write a manifesto to connect the focus points on nutrition in the current council period. The Partij voor de Dieren is in opposition in the city council, and also focuses on a better food policy. De Buurtbuik cooks free meals from food that would otherwise be thrown away, where everyone is welcome to join. This brings local residents together. In Sustainable Utrecht 2030, a trial with subsidised organic groceries was carried out in Lunetten. A social entrepreneur creates a market garden in the city, on Kanaleneiland, a neighbourhood that is under social pressure. He enjoys gardening and growing food. The goal is to grow and sell food very locally. He is going to talk to the municipality about using open spaces in the city to grow food. Three students from Utrecht University are taking the course Knowledge for Society and would like to do an assignment for Sustainable Utrecht 2030. Two journalism students from the University of Applied Sciences Utrecht published an interview and an article about this workshop on the website of the University of Applied Sciences and are curious. HovenHier is in contact with Straatboer in Zwolle, who are coming to Utrecht. They flip tiles into large gardens of social housing to create new community gardens. A visitor tries to live sustainably in practice. A Groen Links city councillor is working on sustainability in daily life and sustainable food and is committed to the Sustainable Development Goals.

The participants brainstormed in three groups about organic food, social vegetable gardening and mobility poverty.

Mobility poverty

Where is mobility poverty?

- Students already receive a public transport card and can cycle by bike.
- People with a non-western migration background often have a different transport tradition, cannot cycle, and prefer a car.
- A car owner is often asked, "can I borrow your car?" But who will pay any fines? In Utrecht, there are websites to match supply and demand of shared cars.
- Transport inequality mainly affects older elderly people with less money, and there is a difference in the provision of public transport between the city and the region. In rural areas, many bus lines are being cancelled. Carriers like to concentrate their offerings on thick lines, but there is a greater need for thinner lines in and outside the city. In the Utrecht city council, there is a discussion about improving the offer of more fine-grained public transport connections, with smaller buses and on weekends.

- There is little transport information for non-Dutch-speaking travellers, and people who are not digitally skilled cannot use apps and therefore miss information about bus and train cancellations and delays. An analog alternative is not well thought out, for people who cannot use IDEAL and DigiD. For example, there are 60,000 low-literate people in Utrecht. Older people often depend on their children for the use of apps, and that sometimes goes wrong.
- There is a gap in accessibility between people who are digitally literate and those who are not. Who needs help, and how can people be helped in an accessible way? Many elderly people go to community centers, but not everyone. Home care comes to people's homes, and if these employees were given more time, they could inform people.
- In Utrecht, residents can apply for a parking card for visitors, but if that doesn't work, not all officials can help you properly. Elderly people who do not have IDEAL and DigiD cannot install their visitor app themselves. It can help if someone helps them step by step, but that takes time. There is also a discussion about free parking for caregivers and home care. That sounds sympathetic, but it can dissuade people from sustainable alternatives such as the bicycle.
- The costs of public transport and sustainable mobility are often a problem, but free public transport is an untargeted solution. An offer for free public transport for young school children has recently been extended by one year. The public transport card for students teaches them how to travel by train. Even after graduation, they are more likely to rent a shared car or travel by public transport. This lowers the threshold for getting acquainted with public transport and cycling.
- Being assertive and thinking out of the box is often assumed, but you have to learn that. This is difficult, for example, for older Turkish women.
- Accessibility is not just about means of transport. Can you safely take your walker across the sidewalk to the store? Crossing bike paths can be dangerous, especially with children. There are fewer zebra crossings in Utrecht. Officials defend that choice, arguing that cyclists don't care. If you make it mandatory to stop, you also send a signal, which makes cyclists pay more attention. Parents with young children and the elderly are afraid to cross the road when there are no traffic lights.
- What is possible? Abroad, it is easier to hail a taxi on the street (with a group) with a show of hands. Here, you need to use an app or phone. The Netherlands is leading the way with a digital environment, but how do we ensure that everyone can participate?
- Integration programmes for newcomers should pay more attention to bicycle deals: an offer of a cheap bicycle that is maintained for a year. Not everyone in the target group knows about this. The cyclists' union visits people who have a bicycle in their shed and refurbishes them for these bicycle deals, especially in Overvecht.
- In some neighborhoods, you can call a neighborhood cellphone, which someone will use to pick you up and bring you by car or an electric golf cart. This depends on volunteers. The quality of the professional regional taxi for the less mobile could be higher. One problem is the tight labour market, which means there is a lack of drivers.
- There are many great initiatives, but the offer is too little for the large group, especially older people.
- Students from the HAS University of Applied Sciences are conducting research into mobility poverty, and have drawn up a survey in Dutch, English and Arabic, among other things. With Arabic you reach many asylum seekers who can read Arabic, but older Moroccans and young people who travel in dirty vans cannot read Arabic.

Fill out the survey here:

Dutch: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1xbC2uE1xBFAbbETcntBHVDg8Mz78-M9rBwm0auitG1w/edit>

English: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/14Xe81qgRsyqDRDNDOHENdTJzHuhjosTx0gY9wuuvRTc/edit>

Arabic: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/12BPFWRQ8AOeGHi77nhbD5aXzJp2hj5vMKh4w00ea6qc/edit>

Subsidised Organic Groceries brainstorm group

During this brainstorming session the group discussed a variety of issues surrounding affordable and sustainable food as well as what initiatives are dealing with this in Utrecht. There were altogether 6 participants in the brainstorm session - 2 interns from Duurzaam Utrecht 2030, 3 students from Utrecht University Global Sustainability Science bachelor's program and a representative from the organisation BuurtBuik Utrecht.

Most of the participants of the brainstorm session were vegetarian and vegan and considered sustainability of their food in their daily life. Many mentioned the fact that organic produce is too expensive although they would want to purchase it.

We spent a good portion of the time talking about the subsidized organic grocery project we have conducted so far. Participants were interested in the feedback on the vouchers we were giving out at the community centre Limoenz - overall the feedback was really good, and most people interviewed were interested in sustainability and expressed a wish to shop more organic produce but not being able to due to the affordability.

We also had some discussion on how the regular organic supermarkets have a very specific aesthetic and feel to them - we all agreed that when you enter an average organic food store you feel immediately that it is meant for well off people. It is not only the prices that indicate this but also the atmosphere and how everything seems so beige, and the fresh produce is rarely the centrepiece of the store. This is similar to the feedback gotten from the interviews at community centre Limoenz about the store Ekovers which was part of the project. But this time we were discussing organic stores in general. As a better alternative multiple Turkish, Persian, or other stores were brought up by participants. For example, Persepolis on Twijnstraat or Sweet Greens next to IBB.

Elizabete asked for any feedback and thoughts on Duurzaam Utrecht's 2030 ongoing project (giving out vouchers) as well as our current plans for the project's continuation which consists of 3 parts:

Buy 1, give 1 initiative where regular visitors of organic supermarkets are encouraged to buy an extra product (fresh produce specifically) for someone else. This could be distributed in 2 ways: either the shop delivers the produce to food banks weekly or putting up receipts in windows making it known that there is paid for produce available.

it was agreed that putting up the receipts in windows would be easier to organize logistically and this is an initiative that has worked well in other countries.

One participant brought up the aspect of shame that people might feel going and asking for the paid for produce - this depends on the context and culture and needs to be researched closer in the context of Utrecht.

It was brought up that it might be good to contact sustainable food suppliers directly and see if there is a direct collaboration possible there.

We talked in detail about BuurtBuik (<https://buurtbuik.nl/over-ons/>) and the work they do. It is a volunteer-led organization that collects leftover food from food banks, local grocery stores and other organizations and cooks a three-course meal which they give out at events in different neighbourhoods. This way they decrease food waste, cook food in creative ways (often they get a very random combination of products) and bring the community together with their events.

We discussed how larger supermarket chains contribute largely to food waste and why they rarely agree to donate food for organizations like BuurtBuik for example. One participant works in a supermarket chain and mentioned that they are not allowed to take home the leftover bread at the end of the day - it just gets thrown out. There could be reasons like stricter regulations for food safety (stores do not want to take on responsibility for consequences), additional work for the employees in an already complicated system they are working in and so on. This is something that can be explored more in the future.

Students from UU mentioned another volunteer-led organization called Grounded (<https://www.grounded-community.org>) that organized a three-course meal from locally and sustainably grown produce. They also have a permanent location in Utrecht Science Park where it is possible to buy

ready-made meals and snacks as well as fresh produce at a reasonable price. This is another organization to possibly collaborate with in the future.

Social vegetable gardening and increasing biodiversity in Utrecht

Many topics were discussed in the group, and resources shared between the participants, including links to good collaborators, and helping each other with future plans. There were 4 participants in the brainstorm, two people who work in increasing gardening in Utrecht, one member of local government (Partij voor de Dieren), and a member of the Utrecht food council.

Some of the topics of discussion were:

- There is an ideal example of community involvement in Leidsche Rijn, just as you cross over the yellow bridge. Members from one of the high-rise apartments have started a vegetable garden on spare land behind the apartment complex. This is an ideal community initiative, since it shows that people from an area are willing to make a garden for their own use. We discussed the importance of mobilizing people in their own community, so that they have ownership over their own initiatives.
- There was a discussion on greening of school yards. It was noted that there is subsidy for this, that the schools can apply for. It's something that schools usually want, but they are too busy to do it for themselves. This can be an opportunity to work in a green area and do some good in the community. However, one member noted that during his work greening a schoolyard, the children often trample the flower gardens. The recommendation is to only use trees or have vegetable gardens that are fenced off. These can be used for education of the children.
- A large problem that was discussed is that many initiatives that are started by local government (and others) rely too much on volunteers. There was a general agreement that this is not good enough, and that to truly change our society as much as is needed green jobs need to be better recognized and paid for, rather than focussing on high-wage technology jobs.
- Another topic for how to take ownership of the local area/neighbourhood is the 'Right to challenge', or 'Bewonersbod' that the Utrecht Gemeente offers. <https://www.utrecht.nl/bestuur-en-organisatie/initiatief-en-invloed/uw-initiatief/bewonersbod/> . This allows local residents to take over some of the jobs of the municipality, for example caretaking of green spaces, and saving leaves for composting. This can take a long time, since sometimes the local government has awarded multi-year contracts to other contractors. In this way, local communities can take ownership, and use their own land.
- One idea that was discussed was how to create a market garden style setup within the bounds of the city, so that local residents can come and buy fresh food. This used to be done within the bounds of the city but isn't any longer. There are many types of these farms, but most run purely off subscription, which makes it difficult for those on low incomes.
- It can be quite a problem for the municipality to keep land within the city, most of the land is in private ownership and once it is owned privately it is usually lost to these types of initiatives. One idea though is to use more roofs for gardens, as this space is often underutilised.
- The main topic that was ongoing throughout the discussion was how to make sure that people were mobilised within their own communities and could benefit from their own ideas and projects. Particularly difficult in poorer neighbourhoods, where people are often working multiple jobs and have less free time.

SUSTAINABLE LIVING AT UNIVERSITY COLLEGE UTRECHT

UCU STUDENTS SHARED THEIR IDEAS FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVING

By Giulia Malisani

During the University College Utrecht Sustainability Week in November 2023, we hosted a silent brainstorming session aimed at exploring sustainable living ideas among the university community. This

innovative approach allowed participants to silently share their thoughts on eco-friendly practices, sustainability aspirations, and challenges, fostering a reflective and inclusive environment. The event brought together students and faculty, yielding diverse insights into sustainability desires and obstacles, such as the need for more campus initiatives, affordable sustainable options, and enhanced community support. The collected ideas from this session will be pivotal for shaping future sustainability projects at UCU and the wider Utrecht area.

STREET SURVEYS IN THE CITY CENTRE

UTRECHT RESIDENTS SHARED THEIR IDEAS FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVING

By Giulia Malisani

In December 2023, we conducted street interviews in Utrecht's city centre to gather insights on sustainable living from the community. A wide range of residents shared their experiences with sustainability, including their efforts, aspirations, and obstacles. Topics ranged from recycling and public transportation use to challenges like the need for more information and affordable sustainable options.

These conversations offered a glimpse into the community's willingness to adopt greener lifestyles and the barriers they face. The feedback will inform future sustainability strategies in Utrecht, highlighting the importance of community engagement in environmental policy development.

ONLINE SURVEY

UTRECHT RESIDENTS SHARED THEIR IDEAS FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVING

By Giulia Malisani

In December 2023, we launched an online survey to tap into the perspectives of Utrecht residents regarding sustainable living. This digital outreach was designed to capture a broad spectrum of views, experiences, and suggestions for enhancing environmental sustainability within the city. Participants from various backgrounds contributed, enriching our understanding of the community's current sustainable practices, aspirations, and the challenges they encounter. The specific results are illustrated in the following table.

Age:	Gender:	Neighbourhood of residency	What sustainable practices do you currently engage in? (e.g., recycling, using public transportation, composting kitchen waste...). List as many as you like.	What additional steps or actions would you like to take to live more sustainably? List as many as you like.	Referring to the answers you gave above, what challenges or obstacles are preventing you from implementing these changes? List as many as you like.	What do you think the government should be doing to make sustainable living more accessible? Please share your thoughts.	Do you feel that your individual actions can have a positive impact on sustainability? (Yes/No). Optional: feel free to provide a reason for your answer in "Other".
59	Female	Dichterwijk	No Black Friday. Use bicycle and trains. Recycling cans, glass, paper. Volunteer at Buurtbuik (cook with food that would be wasted) for the neighbourhood.	Sell stuff I don't use. Or give it away.	It takes time and focus.	Raise taxes for toxic materials. Make it easy and popular to recycle and produce quality fabrics. Stop pushing	Yes

			Accidently plandeling. Use products extensively and repair instead of buying new. Vintage shopping.			consuming and buying.	
20	Woman	East/Schildersbuurt	public transport, buying second hand clothing and items, consuming responsibly	buy more local foods instead of exotic flown in foods	Prices and knowledge		Yes
20	Woman	Oost/Wilhelmina Park/University College Utrecht	Vegetarian, public transport, second hand clothing only, voting left, no/low heating but blankets instead, water bottle, lower electricity use	Compost kitchen waste and recycling	Living on a campus	Maybe a program for students	Yes
20	woman	Utrecht Oost	recycling, using public transportation, composting kitchen waste, thrifting clothes, and items, cycling, keeping radiators off, eating vegetarian, buying less	using less plastic, generating sustainable energy	money available, products available	enforce more restrictions on supermarkets and companies, more taxes for businesses	Yes
23	Female	Galgenwaard en omgeving	Using public transport, biking, recycling	Composting kitchen waste	I don't put the effort and i live with other people	Makes prices for sustainable goods more accessible	Yes
56	Female		Recycling, composting kitchen waste, bev, water recycling, photovoltaic panels, and farmer for own use	Using second-hand clothes, raising animals	Time, Money, and more info	Increase schooling, more info and instructions for use, greater involvement, more economic funds	Yes
60	Male		Recycling, composting kitchen, Bev, water recycling, photovoltaic panels Farmer for own use	Using second-hand clothes Raising animals	Time, money, and more info	Increase schooling, more information and instruction for use. Greater involvement, more economic funds	Yes
19	Female	Wileminapark	Recycling, using public transport/cycling, too good to go, buying discounted food, not wasting food, limiting my general consumption	Reduce plastic consumption, a lot of products come in plastic, so it's unavoidable to buy plastic but maybe by going to the market more often or shops without packaged produce, I can accomplish this.	Time and cost	Reduce plastic packaging, promote organic products that are farmed without completely depleting the soil - work towards this becoming the norm so that the prices aren't more expensive.	Yes and no, because we can obviously do our part and reduce our footprint, but larger, transformative changes must also occur by those in power.
20	Male	Oudwijk	Recycling, bike and train, very little meat, short showers, lights out, almost no radiator on, buy little	Composting, look at place of origin of food I buy,	Limited money, and combined housing	Subsidies for temperature boilers	A bit, but it makes us focus on ourselves whereas we should focus on the larger institutional

							changes that could be implemented.
19	questioning (afab)	Oost	vegan diet, separating waste, travelling mostly by bike,	I would like to recycle more - now I only separate glass and paper, while plastic is being thrown with general waste	The only bins available are glass-paper-general	Implement a more recyclable policy in terms of waste	Yes
19	male	Oost	recycling, cycling, turning lights off, vegetarian	fly less, eat more organic vegetables,	i am an international student. organic vegetables are more expensive than non-organic vegetables	give vouchers	Yes
19	Woman	Utrecht Oost	Recycling, vegan ish, biking, public transport	Want to go fully vegan, fly less	Moneyyyy	Decrease sustainable costs	Yes
68	M	Lombok	Energy (warmtepomp), no car, bike & public transport, minimal clothes buying, vegetarian, minimal flying	Further reduce flying	I like to travel, a lot	Not for me	Yes
69	Man	City of Utrecht	Organize waste separate, shop biological food, balanced use of car and public traffic, endless repairing equipment.	Using equipment as long as possible, repair of equipment.	Limited income	Creating law.	All little efforts will help
33	Male	Central	Less animal protein. Buying more sustainable produce.	I would like to take more steps towards the aforementioned practices.	Financial implications. Logistical implications.	Absolutely. In terms of public procurement, raising awareness, or food policy.	Yes
58	F	Zeeheldenbuurt	Waste separation, live without car, solar panels, vegetarian diet, limited dairy consumption, low consumption of other goods,	Can't think of anymore	None	Yes! Can provide subsidies for sustainable transportation and sustainable energy, can implement (local) restrictions on unsustainable practices. Make it easier for people to make responsible choices.	Yes, if everyone does their bit, it adds up!

ANNEX: PROGRAMME

Sustainable Utrecht 2030:

Enable sustainable living on a tight budget

Welcome and introduction

Come by for a warm welcome, an introduction to *Sustainable Utrecht 2030*, an overview of the agenda of the day and a short icebreaker.

Open stage

A platform to inspire and be inspired: share your contributions to social justice and sustainability in Utrecht.

Focus Groups Discussions

Share your thoughts and brainstorm your ideas on one of these three topics:

- *Subsidized organic groceries*: We discuss affordable, sustainable food choices.
 - *Social vegetable gardening*: we explore communal green spaces.
 - *Mobility poverty*: how do we tackle transport inequalities?
-

Concluding insights and steps forward

A reflection on the most important insights and a short discussion about the future steps towards a sustainable Utrecht.

Coffee, snacks, and networking

Find new interesting connections and collaborations in an informal atmosphere.

Join us on a journey to a greener, fairer Utrecht.

